

New properties of gb^* –closed map and gb^* -open map in topological spaces

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Abstract: In this paper, we some of their properties of semi-open, α -open, pre-open, α -open sets to induced topology, we compare with the semi-open or (b -open, pre-open, α -open) set if for the topological space and the topological space induced, finally we inntroduce a new properties for gb^* -closed maps and gb^* -open map in topological space induced.

Key words: semi-open set, α -open set, gb^* –closed map, gb^* -open map.

1. Introduction and preliminaries

Different types of closed and open were studied by various researchers. The notion of b -open sets was introduced by D. Andrijevic [4] in the year 1968. A. A. Omari et al [1] made an analytical study and result the concepts of generalized b -closed sets in topological spaces. The idea of introduced regular generalized b -closed map in topological space by S. Sekar and K. Mariappa [13] in 2013. A new class of generalised b star- closed map in Topological Spaces was introduced in 2017 by S. Sekar et al [14].

The aim of this paper is to continue the study of new properties of b star-closed maps in topological spaces one of its properties are based on the induced topology and compares the state of a set with respect to the topological subspace and the total topological space in the following positions. Throughout the present paper, $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$ and (\mathcal{F}, Σ) will denote topological spaces with no separation properties assumed. For a subset Ω of a topological space $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$, $cl(\Omega)$ and $int(\Omega)$ will denote the closure and interior of Ω in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$, respectively.

We recall the following definitions which are useful in the sequel.

Definition 1.1. Let a subset Ω of a topological space $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$ is called

- (1) a pre-open set [2], if $\Omega \subseteq int(cl(\Omega))$.
- (2) a semi-open set [10], if $\Omega \subseteq cl(int(\Omega))$.
- (3) a α -open set [2], if $\Omega \subseteq int(cl(int(\Omega)))$.
- (4) a b -open set [4], if $\Omega \subseteq cl(int(\Omega)) \cup int(cl(\Omega))$.

Remark 1.1. The b -closed (resp. semi-closed, pre-closed, α -closed) of a subset Ω of a space $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$ is the intersection of all b -closure (resp. semi-closed, pre-closed, α -closed) sets that contain Ω and is denoted by $bcl(\Omega)$ (resp. $scl(\Omega)$, $pcl(\Omega)$, $\alpha cl(\Omega)$).

Remark 1.2. The b -open (resp. semi-open, pre-open, α -open) of a contained in Ω of a space $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$ is the union of all b -interior (resp. semi-interior, pre-interior, α -interior) sets that Contained in Ω and is denoted by $b-int(\Omega)$ (resp. $s-int(\Omega)$, $p-int(\Omega)$, $\alpha-int(\Omega)$).

Definition 1.2. Let a subset Ω of a topological space $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$ is called

- (1) a generalized closed set (briefly g -closed) [9], if $cl(\Omega) \subseteq \theta$ whenever $\Omega \subseteq \theta$ and θ is open in \mathcal{E} .
- (2) a generalized b -closed set (briefly gb -closed) [1], if $bcl(\Omega) \subseteq \theta$ whenever $\Omega \subseteq \theta$ and θ is open in \mathcal{E} .
- (3) a α generalized $*$ -closed set (briefly αg^* -closed) [8], if $cl(\Omega) \subseteq int(\theta)$ whenever $\Omega \subseteq \theta$ and θ is α -open in \mathcal{E} .
- (4) a $g * s$ -closed set (briefly $g * s$ -closed) [3], if $scl(\Omega) \subseteq \theta$ whenever $\Omega \subseteq \theta$ and θ is gs -open in \mathcal{E} .
- (5) a regular generalized b -closed set (briefly rgb -closed) [5] if $scl(\Omega) \subseteq \theta$ whenever $\Omega \subseteq \theta$ and θ is regular open in \mathcal{E} .

Definition 1.3. [14] Let \mathcal{E} and \mathcal{F} be topological spaces. A map $\phi : (\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{T})$ is called generalized b star-closed (briefly, gb^* -closed map) if the image of every closed set in \mathcal{E} is gb^* -closed in \mathcal{F} .

Definition 1.4. [14] Let \mathcal{E} and \mathcal{F} be topological spaces. A map $\phi : (\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{T})$ is called generalized b star open (briefly, gb^* -open) if the image of every open set in \mathcal{E} is gb^* -open in \mathcal{F} .

2. Main Results

In this section, we study the behavior of pre-open sets, b -open sets, α -open sets and b -closed sets and g -closed sets in a sub-space. For simplification, we introduce the following Remark and Notation.

Notation 2.1. Let \mathcal{E}_0 be a nonempty set endowed with the induced topology of $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$, we denote $(\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0)$.

Notation 2.2. Let a subset Ω of a topological space $(\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0)$, we give the following set $cl_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega)$, $int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega)$, $bcl_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega)$, $b-int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega)$ and $scl_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega)$ according to their definitions but in relation to the induced topology.

Remark 2.1. Let a subset Ω of a topological space $(\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0)$, we have

$$cl_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega) = cl(\Omega) \cap \mathcal{E}_0, \quad int(\Omega) \subseteq int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega). \quad (1)$$

The principle of the following theorem, we study the behavior of pre-open sets a sub-space.

Theorem 2.1. Let a subset Ω of a topological space \mathcal{E}_0 , such as $cl(\Omega) \subset \mathcal{E}_0 \subset \mathcal{E}$ and Ω is pre-open in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$. Then Ω is pre-open in $(\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0)$, but not conversely.

Proof. Let Ω is pre-open in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$, by (1), we get that $\Omega \subseteq int(cl(\Omega)) \subseteq int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(cl(\Omega))$, since $cl_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega) = cl(\Omega) \cap \mathcal{E}_0 = cl(\Omega)$, then $\Omega \subseteq int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(cl(\Omega) \cap \mathcal{E}_0) = int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(cl_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega))$. Hence Ω is pre-open in $(\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0)$. \square

Remark 2.2. If $(\mathbb{R}, \mathcal{T}_u)$ endowed with the usual topology, then $(\mathbb{N}, \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{N}))$ is the induced topology.

Example 2.1. Let $\mathcal{E} = \mathbb{R}$, $\mathcal{E}_0 = \mathbb{N}$ and $\Omega = \{1, 2\}$, we have $cl(\Omega) = \Omega$, $int(cl(\Omega)) = \emptyset$ and $int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(cl_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega)) = \Omega$. Hence Ω is pre-open in the topology for \mathbb{N} and Ω is not pre-open in \mathbb{R} .

The following result is a direct consequence of Theorem 2.1.

Corollary 2.1. Let a subset Ω of a topological space \mathcal{E}_0 , such as $cl(\Omega) \subset \mathcal{E}_0 \subset \mathcal{E}$, then $p-int(\Omega) \subseteq pint_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega)$.

Proof. Let a subset Ω of a topological space \mathcal{E}_0 , we note $\Upsilon_0 = \{\theta \subset \Omega : \theta \text{ is pre-open in } (\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0)\}$ and $\Upsilon = \{\theta \subset \Omega : \theta \text{ is pre-open in } (\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})\}$. By Theorem 2.1, we get $\Upsilon \subset \Upsilon_0$, which implies that

$$p-int(\Omega) = \bigcup_{\theta \in \Upsilon} \theta \subseteq \bigcup_{\theta \in \Upsilon_0} \theta = p-int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega).$$

□

The principle of the following theorem, we study the behavior of b -open sets a sub-space.

Theorem 2.2. Let a subset Ω of a topological space \mathcal{E}_0 , such as $cl(\Omega) \subset \mathcal{E}_0 \subset \mathcal{E}$ and Ω is b -open in $(\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0)$. Then Ω is b -open in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$, but not conversely.

Proof. Let a subset Ω of a topological space \mathcal{E}_0 , by (1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega &\subseteq cl_{\mathcal{E}_0}(int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega)) \cup int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(cl_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega)) \subseteq (cl(int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega)) \cap \mathcal{E}_0) \cup int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(cl(\Omega) \cap \mathcal{E}_0) \\ &\subseteq (cl(int(\Omega)) \cap \mathcal{E}_0) \cup int(cl(\Omega) \cap \mathcal{E}_0) \subseteq (cl(int(\Omega)) \cap \mathcal{E}_0) \cup int(cl(\Omega) \cap \mathcal{E}_0). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $cl(int(\Omega)) \cap \mathcal{E}_0 \subset cl(int(\Omega))$ and $int(cl(\Omega) \cap \mathcal{E}_0) \subset int(cl(\Omega))$, which implies that $\Omega \subseteq cl(int(\Omega)) \cup int(cl(\Omega))$, then Ω is semi-open in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$. □

Example 2.2. Let $\mathcal{E} = \mathbb{R}$, $\mathcal{E}_0 = \mathbb{N}$ and $\Omega = \{1, 2\}$, then $int(cl(\Omega)) = cl(int(\Omega)) = \emptyset$ and $cl_{\mathcal{E}_0}(int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega)) = int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(cl_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega)) = \Omega$. Hence Ω is b -open in $(\mathbb{N}, \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{N}))$ and Ω is not b -open in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathcal{T}_u)$.

Corollary 2.2. Let a subset Ω of a topological space \mathcal{E}_0 , such as $cl(\Omega) \subset \mathcal{E}_0 \subset \mathcal{E}$, then $b-int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega) \subseteq b-int(\Omega)$.

Proof. Let Ω be set in \mathcal{E}_0 , we note $\Theta_0 = \{\theta \subset \Omega : \theta \text{ is } b\text{-open in } (\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0)\}$ and $\Theta = \{\theta \subset \Omega : \theta \text{ is } b\text{-open in } (\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})\}$. By Theorem 2.2, we get $\Theta_0 \subset \Theta$, which implies that

$$b-int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega) = \bigcup_{\theta \in \Theta_0} \theta \subseteq \bigcup_{\theta \in \Theta} \theta = b-int(\Omega).$$

□

The principle of the following theorem, we study the behavior of α -open sets a sub-space.

Theorem 2.3. Let a subset Ω of a topological space \mathcal{E}_0 , such as $cl(\Omega) \subset \mathcal{E}_0 \subset \mathcal{E}$ and Ω is α -open in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$. Then Ω is α -open in $(\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0)$, but not conversely.

Proof. By remark 2.1, we have

$$cl(int(\Omega)) \subseteq cl(int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega)) \subseteq cl(int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega)) \cap \mathcal{E}_0 = cl_{\mathcal{E}_0}(int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega)).$$

Then,

$$int(cl(int(\Omega))) \subseteq int(cl_{\mathcal{E}_0}(int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega))) \subseteq int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(cl_{\mathcal{E}_0}(int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega))).$$

Since Ω is α -open in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$, then $\Omega \subseteq int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(cl_{\mathcal{E}_0}(int_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega)))$. Hence Ω is α -open in $(\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0)$. □

Example 2.3. Let $\mathcal{E} = \mathbb{R}$, $\mathcal{E}_0 = \mathbb{N}$ and $\Omega = \{1, 2\}$, then $\text{int}(cl(\text{int}(\Omega))) = \emptyset$ and $\text{int}_{\mathcal{E}_0}(cl_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\text{int}_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega))) = \Omega$. Hence Ω is α -open in the topology for \mathbb{N} and Ω is not α -open in the topology for \mathbb{R} .

Corollary 2.3. Let a subset Ω of a topological space \mathcal{E}_0 , such as $cl(\Omega) \subset \mathcal{E}_0 \subset \mathcal{E}$, then $\alpha\text{-int}(\Omega) \subseteq \alpha\text{-int}_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega)$.

Proof. Let Ω be set in \mathcal{E}_0 , we note $\Xi_0 = \{\theta \subset \Omega : \theta \text{ is } \alpha\text{-open in } (\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0)\}$ and $\Xi = \{\theta \subset \Omega : \theta \text{ is } \alpha\text{-open in } (\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})\}$. By Theorem 2.3, we get $\Xi \subset \Xi_0$, which implies that

$$\alpha\text{-int}(\Omega) = \bigcup_{\theta \in \Xi} \theta \subseteq \bigcup_{\theta \in \Xi_0} \theta = \alpha\text{-int}_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega).$$

□

The principle of the following theorem, we study the behavior of g -closed sets a sub-space.

Theorem 2.4. Let a subset Ω of a topological space \mathcal{E}_0 , such as $\Omega \subset \mathcal{E}_0 \subset \mathcal{E}$. If Ω is g -closed in $(\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0)$, then Ω is g -closed in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$.

Proof. Assume Ω is g -closed in $(\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0)$. Let θ is open in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$ and $\Omega \subseteq \theta$, with $\Omega \subseteq \theta \cap \mathcal{E}_0$, since $\theta \cap \mathcal{E}_0$ is open in $(\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0)$, then $cl(\Omega) \subseteq \theta \cap \mathcal{E}_0 \subseteq \theta$. Hence Ω is g -closed in \mathcal{E} . □

Theorem 2.5. Let a subset Ω of a topological space \mathcal{E}_0 , such as \mathcal{E}_0 is open in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$, then Ω is g -closed in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$, if and only if Ω is g -closed in $(\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0)$.

Proof. By Theorem 2.4, just show that, Ω is g -closed in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$ implies that Ω is g -closed in $(\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0)$. Indeed, let θ_0 is open in \mathcal{E}_0 , there is an open θ in \mathcal{E} , such that $\theta_0 = \theta \cap \mathcal{E}_0$, if $\Omega \subseteq \theta_0 = \theta \cap \mathcal{E}_0$, since $\theta \cap \mathcal{E}_0$ is open in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$, give us $cl(\Omega) \subseteq \theta_0$ and $cl_{\mathcal{E}_0}(\Omega) \subseteq cl(\Omega)$, then Ω is g -closed in $(\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0)$. □

The following result is some properties of gb^* -closed maps.

Theorem 2.6. Let \mathcal{E}_0 be a closed set and let $\phi : (\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ is gb^* -closed map, then $\phi : (\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ is gb^* -closed map, but not conversely.

Proof. Let $\phi : (\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ is gb^* -closed map and ϑ_0 be an closed set in $(\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0)$. So, it exists is a closed set ϑ in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$, such that $\vartheta_0 = \vartheta \cap \mathcal{E}_0$. As \mathcal{E}_0 is closed in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$. Hence $\phi(\vartheta_0)$ is gb^* -closed in (\mathcal{F}, Σ) . Then $\phi : (\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ is gb^* -closed. □

Example 2.4. Let $\phi : (\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{E}, \Sigma)$ be a map, such that $\phi(x) = x$, $\phi(y) = x$, $\phi(z) = y$, $\phi(t) = z$, where $\mathcal{E} = \{x, y, z, t\}$, $\mathcal{T} = \{\mathcal{E}, \emptyset, \{x\}, \{y, z, t\}\}$, $\Sigma = \{\mathcal{E}, \emptyset, \{y\}, \{x, y, z\}\}$ and $\mathcal{E}_0 = \{x\}$. Then $\phi : (\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0) \rightarrow (\mathcal{E}, \Sigma)$ is gb^* -closed map, but $\phi : (\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{E}, \Sigma)$ is not gb^* -closed map.

Lemma 2.1. Let Ω_1 and Ω_2 are gb^* -closed in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$, then $\Omega_1 \cup \Omega_2$ is gb^* -closed in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$.

Proof. Let Ω_1 and Ω_2 are gb^* -closed in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$, if $bcl(\Omega_1 \cup \Omega_2) \subseteq \theta$, with θ is g^* open in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$, we have $bcl(\Omega_1) \subset bcl(\Omega_1 \cup \Omega_2) \subseteq \theta$, then $\Omega_1 \subseteq \theta$, the same way we find $\Omega_2 \subseteq \theta$. Hence $\Omega_1 \cup \Omega_2 \subseteq \theta$. □

Theorem 2.7. Let \mathcal{E}_1 and \mathcal{E}_2 sets in \mathcal{E} and let $\phi : (\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ is map, such as $\mathcal{E}_1 \cup \mathcal{E}_2 = \mathcal{E}$. If $\phi_{\mathcal{E}_1} : (\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{T}_1) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ and $\phi_{\mathcal{E}_2} : (\mathcal{E}_2, \mathcal{T}_2) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ are gb^* -closed map, then $\phi : (\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ is gb^* -closed map.

Proof. Let $\phi_{\mathcal{E}_1} : (\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{T}_1) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$, $\phi_{\mathcal{E}_2} : (\mathcal{E}_2, \mathcal{T}_2) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ are gb^* -closed map and ϑ be an closed set in \mathcal{E} , then

$$\begin{aligned}\phi(\vartheta) &= \phi(\vartheta \cap \mathcal{E}) = \phi(\vartheta \cap (\mathcal{E}_1 \cup \mathcal{E}_2)) = \phi((\vartheta \cap \mathcal{E}_1) \cup (\vartheta \cap \mathcal{E}_2)) \\ &= \phi(\vartheta \cap \mathcal{E}_1) \cup \phi(\vartheta \cap \mathcal{E}_2).\end{aligned}$$

We have $\vartheta \cap \mathcal{E}_1$ and $\vartheta \cap \mathcal{E}_2$ are a closed in $(\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{T}_1)$ and $(\mathcal{E}_2, \mathcal{T}_2)$, respectively, then $\phi(\vartheta \cap \mathcal{E}_1)$ and $\phi(\vartheta \cap \mathcal{E}_2)$ are gb^* -closed in (\mathcal{F}, Σ) . By lemma 2.1, we get that $\phi(\vartheta \cap \mathcal{E}_1)$ and $\phi(\vartheta \cap \mathcal{E}_2)$ are gb^* -closed in (\mathcal{F}, Σ) . Hence $\phi(\vartheta)$ is gb^* -closed in (\mathcal{F}, Σ) . Then $\phi : (\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ is gb^* -closed. \square

The following corollary is a new generalization of the Theorem 2.7.

Corollary 2.4. *Let $\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{E}_2, \dots, \mathcal{E}_n$ be sets, such as $\mathcal{E} = \bigcup_{i=1}^{i=n} \mathcal{E}_i$, if $\phi_{\mathcal{E}_i} : (\mathcal{E}_i, \mathcal{T}_i) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ is gb^* -closed map, for $i \in [1, n] \cap \mathbb{N}$, then $\phi : (\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ is gb^* -closed map.*

The following result is some properties of gb^* -open map.

Theorem 2.8. *Let \mathcal{E}_0 be a open set in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$ and let $\phi : (\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ is gb^* -open map, then $\phi : (\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ is gb^* -open map, but not conversely.*

Proof. Let $\phi : (\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ is gb^* -closed map and θ_0 be an open set in $(\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0)$. So, it exists is a open set θ in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$, such that $\theta_0 = \theta \cap \mathcal{E}_0$. As \mathcal{E}_0 is open in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$. Hence $\phi(\theta_0)$ is gb^* -open in (\mathcal{F}, Σ) . Then $\phi : (\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}_0) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ is gb^* -open. \square

Example 2.5. *Let $\phi : (\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{E}, \Sigma)$ be a map such that $\phi(x) = x$, $\phi(y) = x$, $\phi(c) = y$, $\phi(d) = c$, where $\mathcal{E} = \{x, y, c, d\}$, $\mathcal{T} = \{\mathcal{E}, \emptyset, \{x\}, \{y, c, d\}\}$, $\Sigma = \{\mathcal{E}, \emptyset, \{y\}, \{x, y, c\}\}$ and $\mathcal{E}_0 = \{x\}$. Then $\phi : (\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{E}, \Sigma)$ is gb^* -open map, but $\phi : (\mathcal{E}_0, \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{E}, \Sigma)$ is not gb^* -open map.*

Lemma 2.2. *Let Ω_1 and Ω_2 are gb^* -open in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$, such as $\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2 \neq \emptyset$, then $\Omega_1 \cup \Omega_2$ is gb^* -open in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$.*

Proof. Let Ω_1 and Ω_2 are gb^* -open in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$, such as $\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2 \neq \emptyset$, we have \emptyset is gb^* -closed, then $(\Omega_1 \cup \Omega_2)^c$ is gb^* -closed in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$, thus $\Omega_1 \cup \Omega_2$ is gb^* -open in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$. \square

Theorem 2.9. *Let $\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{E}_2$ be sets disjoint, such as $\mathcal{E}_1 \cup \mathcal{E}_2 = \mathcal{E}$. If $\phi_{\mathcal{E}_1} : (\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{T}_1) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ and $\phi_{\mathcal{E}_2} : (\mathcal{E}_2, \mathcal{T}_2) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ are gb^* -open map, $\phi : \mathcal{E} \rightarrow \mathcal{F}$ is an injective map, then $\phi : (\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ is gb^* -open map.*

Proof. Let $\phi_{\mathcal{E}_1} : (\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{T}_1) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ and $\phi_{\mathcal{E}_2} : (\mathcal{E}_2, \mathcal{T}_2) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ are gb^* -open map, θ be an open set in $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T})$, then

$$\phi(\theta) = \phi(\theta \cap \mathcal{E}) = \phi(\theta \cap \mathcal{E}_1) \cup \phi(\theta \cap \mathcal{E}_2).$$

We have $\theta \cap \mathcal{E}_1$ and $\theta \cap \mathcal{E}_2$ are a open in $(\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{T}_1)$ and $(\mathcal{E}_2, \mathcal{T}_2)$, respectively, then $\phi(\theta \cap \mathcal{E}_1)$ and $\phi(\theta \cap \mathcal{E}_2)$ are gb^* -open in (\mathcal{F}, Σ) , now we show that $\phi(\theta \cap \mathcal{E}_1) \cap \phi(\theta \cap \mathcal{E}_2) = \emptyset$. Suppose that $\phi(\theta \cap \mathcal{E}_1) \cap \phi(\theta \cap \mathcal{E}_2) \neq \emptyset$, let $y \in \phi(\theta \cap \mathcal{E}_1) \cap \phi(\theta \cap \mathcal{E}_2)$, there exists $x_1 \in \mathcal{E}_1$ and $x_2 \in \mathcal{E}_2$, such that, $x_1 \neq x_2$ and $y = \phi(x_1) = \phi(x_2)$, which contradicts, by ϕ is injective map. By lemma 2.2, we get $\phi(\theta)$ is gb^* -open in (\mathcal{F}, Σ) . Then $\phi : (\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ is gb^* -open. \square

The following results are consequences of Theorem 2.9.

Corollary 2.5. *Let $\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{E}_2, \dots, \mathcal{E}_n$ be sets, such as $\mathcal{E} = \bigcup_{i=1}^{i=n} \mathcal{E}_i$ and for $i \neq j$, $\mathcal{E}_i \cap \mathcal{E}_j = \emptyset$. If, for $i \in [1, n] \cap \mathbb{N}$, $\phi_{\mathcal{E}_i}$ is gb^* -open map, then $\phi : (\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{F}, \Sigma)$ is gb^* -open map.*

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